

EUDP IEA Wind - Floating Wind Arrays

Marine growth along the mesopelagic zone

Report
Project No 11826846

23 April 2024

Prepared for EUDP IDEA: Integrated Design of Floating Wind Arrays <Customer Logo here>

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Approved by: Jacob Tornfeldt Sørensen
Approval date: 23 April 2024
Revision: Final 1.0
Classification: **Open.**
File name: 11826846_EUDP_IDEA_Marine_Growth

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1 Introduction

The inaugural floating wind farm located in the North Sea has a 30-megawatt facility housing five offshore wind turbines. It deviates from conventional fixed foundations anchored to the ocean floor as the turbines are secured to the seabed via mooring lines. This pioneering approach facilitates the deployment of turbines in deeper waters, characterized by heightened wind velocities, thereby exploiting vast oceanic expanses for the generation of renewable wind power. Significantly, nearly 80% of the potential for offshore wind power is situated in these deeper waters. Furthermore, the strategic placement of floating turbines at greater distances from the shore addresses concerns related to visual impact on coastal landscapes.

Although still in its developing stages, floating offshore wind technology holds promise as a pivotal constituent of the renewable energy paradigm. However, its realization as a mainstream solution hinges upon the resolution of pertinent challenges encompassing economic feasibility, design optimization, and the alleviation of opposition from the fishing industry.

Many offshore floating wind farm operators face concerns about unwanted marine growth, commonly known as biofouling, on the dynamic cables that transfer electricity from the turbines to the substation. Biofouling can accumulate on these cables, affecting their efficiency and performance. Researchers and industry experts are actively exploring ways to mitigate biofouling and ensure the smooth operation of floating wind farms. Research programs are underway to address this gap and minimize the impact of offshore wind installations on marine environments.

Marine growth, often referred to as marine fouling or biofouling, is the accumulation and proliferation of marine organisms, including algae and various animals, on submerged surfaces like ship hulls, buoys, piers, offshore platforms, and other underwater structures. This natural process occurs when marine organisms settle and grow on these hard substrate surfaces, and it can have several adverse effects on various industries and marine operations e.g., marine growth can change the metal corrosion processes, leading to local and perforated corrosion or by adding to the weight loads of marine structures, moving the barycenter, and thereby greatly increasing the hydrodynamic loading effect. The effects that influence the loading of offshore structures, are driven by parameters that affect the structural diameter and weight, as well as the increase in mass that affects the hydrodynamic conditions (due to drag).

Within minutes upon introduction of new hard substrates in aquatic environments, fouling organisms will start to colonise the newly introduced surfaces (Callow and Callow 2011). A succession of species composition is expected, due to the organisms competing for space and thus, the climax species community composition will not be met within the first years (Dahl et al. 2016). In the beginning, bacteria, eukaryotic organisms, and fungi attach to the surface, eventually forming a biofilm, which function as the basis for macrofauna to adhere to the surface (Causon and Gill 2018; Callow and Callow 2011). Then follow the macro-biofouling species, which typically are sessile fauna and flora organisms such as bivalves (e.g., mussels and oysters), calcareous polychaetes, barnacles, sea anemones, hydrozoans, bryozoans as well as macroalgae. Also, motile organisms associated with biofouling communities include, among others, crustaceans and motile polychaetes, as

they exploit the debris associated with filter-feeders such as mussels and barnacles.

In conclusion, the advent of floating wind farms in offshore areas in the world marks a significant stride towards harnessing renewable wind power from deeper oceanic expanses. While the technology is still evolving, its potential as a key player in the renewable energy landscape is evident. Overcoming challenges related to economic viability, design optimization, and addressing concerns on how to mitigate biofouling on dynamic cables underscore the commitment to ensuring the efficient and sustainable operation of these innovative energy systems. As the offshore wind sector aims to deliver 40 gigawatts by 2030, a holistic understanding of marine biofouling on floating windfarm structures becomes crucial, guiding the industry towards environmentally responsible practices in its pursuit of clean energy.

1.1 Abiotic conditions of the mesopelagic zone

Mesopelagic marine biofouling represents a compelling ecological phenomenon in a depth of the ocean where sunlight is scarce, and temperatures are consistently low. Unlike shallower waters where sunlight fuels primary production, the deep sea relies on the organic detritus known as marine snow as a primary nutrient source (Turner, 2015). Biofouling in these extreme environments involves the colonization of surfaces by various organisms, ranging from microscopic bacteria to larger invertebrates.

Marine biofouling introduced to hard substrate of offshore wind infrastructure is quite versatile depending on the depth. In the upper water column, the euphotic zone, full light spectrum can penetrate the water column (Figure 1). Such light conditions create an optimal growth area for photosynthetic fouling flora that is competing for space with fouling fauna, ultimately creating a mixed habitat of flora and fauna biota. Such habitat and growth dynamics are changing with depth as the light spectrum is being 'filtered' due to optical properties (see Figure 1). Blue light, due to its high energy properties penetrates the deepest but restricts thereby the adequacy of a growth space for photosynthetic fouling biota.

Figure 1 Light penetration of visible light across the light spectrum throughout the water column (Source: NOAA).

The mesopelagic zone, also known as the twilight zone, represents a critical transition layer in the ocean where the interplay between depth and light creates a fascinating and complex environment. Situated between approximately 200 to 1000 meters below the ocean surface, this realm experiences diminishing sunlight as depth increases. In the upper mesopelagic, residual sunlight penetrates, giving rise to a dim, blue-hued illumination (Mascarenhas and Keck 2018). As one descends further, however, natural light dwindles, and the zone transforms into a perpetual twilight, characterized by the subtle glow of bioluminescent organisms. This delicate balance between diminishing natural light and the radiant display of bioluminescence defines the mesopelagic zone, shaping the behaviours and adaptations of its diverse inhabitants, from elusive squid and lanternfish to other specially adapted organisms that navigate the depths in this intriguing interplay of depth and light.

Apart from light, that is very different in the mesopelagic zone, there is also the temperature gradient that is distinct from temperature conditions of shallower water depths. The mesopelagic zone, spanning depths between 200 to 1000 meters beneath the ocean's surface, exhibits a dynamic interplay of depth and temperature that significantly influences the ecological landscape (Pawlowicz 2013). As one descends into this twilight zone, temperatures steadily decrease with depth, reflecting the broader thermal stratification of the ocean. The upper mesopelagic zone experiences a gradual decline in temperature from the sun-warmed surface waters, creating a discernible temperature gradient. However, the mesopelagic's lower reaches witness a more consistent and colder environment as the influence of surface heating diminishes. This stratification plays a pivotal role in shaping the distribution and migration patterns of marine organisms, as they navigate through the mesopelagic zone in response to the

changing thermal conditions. The intricate relationship between depth and temperature in the mesopelagic zone underscores the critical role this environment plays in the broader oceanic ecosystem. In terms of biofouling, it needs to be considered that low temperatures are affecting the rate of growth and that the rate at which marine biofouling is going to accumulate on hard substrate will be a lot lower (Vinagre et al. 2020).

Combined, light and temperature effects create a unique mesopelagic environment for marine biofouling. As light is limited to non-existent, phytoplankton that would otherwise serve as food source for typical biofouling organisms ceases to exist. What is left to colonize are typically filter-feeding invertebrates such as acorn barnacles and mussels, which often make up the greatest part of macrofouling and can occur down to greatest depths (Foster, 2019, Apolinario and Coutinho, 2009) regardless of the geographical regions.

2 Materials and its specific marine growth

The process of fouling could be defined by a four-stage sequence, with stage one to three representing microfouling with adhesion of macromolecules, followed by bacteria then diatoms and eventually the last stage of macrofouling with larvae and spores for the development of larger marine growth (Wahl, 1989). Apart from the abiotic factors of the environment (e.g. salinity, temperature, pH), physical properties of the material such as surface topography, inclined orientation and chemical cues such as anti-bacterial coatings would affect the amount of growth (Dürr, Edyvean and Ramsden, 2022).

The type of materials used for the submerged structures would influence the marine growth population, thickness, and accretion rates. The offshore floating wind structures are direct substrates for marine growth, consisting of materials such as metal for the chains of mooring lines, polyester for insulation, reinforcements or coatings, and wiring systems for power cables.

Steel is the most common structural material for subsea components, followed by aluminum or magnesium alloys for some specific purposes. Delgado, et. al. (2023) classified biofouling into increasing severity from slime to soft biofouling (e.g. algae, bryozoans) and hard biofouling (e.g. barnacles, mussels, tubeworms), and found that most materials including polyethylene and polyoxymethylene-based materials have a relatively poor antifouling grade, except for copper, and stainless-steel had soft biofouling around 52.85% and hard biofouling 18.42% percentage cover of its surface after six months of deployment.

Therefore, in addition to structural materials, anti-corrosion and anti-biofouling coatings are commonly used in undersea structures to maintain structural integrity and reduce maintenance costs (Munger, Vincent, and Shifler, 2022). As these coatings would be the outermost surface for almost all offshore submerged structures, it would be the most relevant for consideration in this note. Typical coats include metallised or organic based such as epoxy (polyamide) or phenolic, or a combination (zinc-rich epoxy) could be used (Munger, Vincent, nd Shifler, 2022).

The Reliable Data Acquisition Platform for Tidal (ReDAPT) project investigated a variety of coats used in offshore marine renewable energy infrastructures at around 42 m in depth, with clear water visibility, low velocity conditions (Vance, Ellis, and Fileman, 2014). The rate of biologically induced corrosion for uncoated marine grade stainless steel without protection from anodes was in the region of 4 to 5 mm per year (Vance, Ellis, and Fileman, 2014).

Biocidal coatings perform better while epoxy coating systems were found to be intensely fouled and require frequent cleaning. In general, epoxy-based coats fulfill the requirement of protection against saltwater corrosion, while biocidal coats should be considered in cases of high risk of mechanical damage and or low water velocity conditions for their antifouling properties (Vance, Ellis, nd Fileman, 2014). Decision on the type of material or coatings used would be highly dependent on the design needs of the system not within this study.

The current guideline for subsea pipelines is to add 50 mm to the diameter as an allowance for marine growth, but the same allowance would be unrealistic

for cables and mooring lines. Subsea cables have a more complex structure and material layers, incorporating steel strips or wires in a woven configuration to reduce bending and axial stiffness (Griffiths, et. al, 2023). Paschen, Rudolf and Dally (2014) found sheathing material of cables made of thermoplastic polyether or ethylene-propylene products grew from 8 mm to around 60 to 80 mm after one year at 12 m depths. As above, marine growth on subsea cables is highly dependent on the environmental conditions and not well studied.

3 Typical mesopelagic biota and growth thickness

The guidelines provided by the Det Norske Veritas (DNV-GL-ST-0437) gives indications on the expected thickness of the marine growth in the areas in question. Although the guideline is not highly detailed in depth-profile, it provides a brief and useful overview of the marine growth conditions regarding comparison of the sites. The US0W is situated north of the Californian coast. Thickness values of the central Californian coast may often reach 200 mm, however, considering that the location is further north than the central coast, relatively lower thickness of marine growth will most likely be seen. The more north-eastern placements are reported with lower thickness. The SN2 is expected to obtain up to 100 mm thickness in the shallow waters and 50 mm in depths below 40 m, whereas a lower thickness is expected in the NO44, more specifically 60 mm in shallow waters and 30 mm below 40 m.

Table 1 Positions and marine growth expectations of the considered locations for potential OWF. The expected marine thickness is based on recommendations provided in the DNV-GL-ST-0437.

ID	Name	Latitude [deg]	Longitude [deg]	Water depth [m]	Marine growth thickness expectations
US0W	Humboldt	40.928	-124.708	-707	~200mm (less may be expected)
NO44	Utsira Nord	59.411	4.433	-273	2 to 40 m depth: 60mm >40 m depth: 30mm
SN2	Sørlige Nordsjø II	56.5	5	-70	2 to 40 m depth: 100mm >40 m depth: 50mm

The expected growth on the different sites is thus considered to be greater at US0W, compared to the more northern locations. Also, SN2 is expected to contain greater thickness compared to NO44.

However, numerous factors influence the amount and type of marine growth, including salinity, temperature, depth, current speed, and wave exposure, in addition to biological factors such as food availability, larval supply, presence of predators, and the general biology and physiology of the fouling species. The shallow areas are typically the densest on the submerged structures, where the first 40 m carry the largest amount of biomass (e.g., Zettler and Pollehne (2006); Almeida and Coolen (2020)). The photopositive organisms reside here and along with more dense phytoplankton production, and thus create a highly productive ecosystem. Studies (Relini et al. 1994b; Yan et al. 2009) show that the abundance of fish and epifauna decreases with increasing depth. The decrease is not due to sparse numbers of colonizers as the distribution of meroplankton in the upper 300 m of the water column is similar throughout the water column (Apolinario and Coutinho 2009). The waters are rich in larvae of molluscs, barnacles, echinoderms and bryozoans, all of which are important

components of biofouling communities (Apolinario and Coutinho 2009). The decrease in abundance is most often caused by the decrease in temperature and hence establishment of a thermocline, but also the decrease in available light leads to lower primary productivity, which in turn decreases the number of individuals that may be present, due to less available resources.

A study performed in the Dongsha region near Hong Kong, discovered that more species were present on the surface of the submerged material in the top 50 m and was most abundant in the top 10 m. (Yan et al. 2009). The number of species as well as the diversity decreased with increasing depth. Between 25 m and 100 m, the most common organism seen was barnacles (in high densities). At 150 m hydroids and barnacles were seen and below 160 m no macrofouling organisms were found on the mooring system, rope or chain connected to the submerged material.

A study conducted in Brazil by Apolinario and Coutinho (2009) found the following rough distribution on submerged material: sponges, barnacles and abundant amount of sea anemones at 45 m depth, polychaetes and sea anemones at 55 m, Polychaetes and hydrozoans were observed down to approximately 170 m depth. Below this depth biofilm was present, but macrofouling organisms were absent.

Although the studies presented here are situated in entirely different regions of the world, they conclude an overall absence of macrofouling organisms below approximately 160-170 meters depth. Hence, even though the regions these studies were conducted in, represent different surface conditions compared to the areas in question, the vertical zonation of faunal categories may be useful for interpretations, since the distribution of organism categories remain the same throughout the deep offshore waters (Apolinario and Coutinho 2009). An ecosystem such as the ones being developed on structures submerged into the deep sea, may not arrive at climax composition as fast as in the photic zone, due to the before mentioned decreased growth rate. Thus, some individuals may arrive at the structures at later than the time frame of execution within these studies, as species of barnacles, polychaetes, gastropods and corals may be seen in deeper parts (Foster 2019; Pineda and Caswell 1998; Sammarco and Boland 2013), although the abundance and herby added load would be considered minimal.

Thus, the DNV guidelines on marine growth thickness can be provided in the upper ~170 m, where denser and more diverse macrofouling communities are expected to occur. Furthermore, the DNV guideline provides density estimates for use in calculations of 1325 kg m^{-2} (DNV-GL-ST-0437).

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